

The Impact of Employing Treated Straw Fibers on the Mechanical and Durability Attributes of Concrete

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Abstract: Agricultural waste such as rice and wheat straw can be effectively utilized in construction. These plant fibers, known for their high tensile strength and low weight, have garnered considerable interest from academia and industry, particularly in civil engineering, automotive, and packaging sectors. However, natural fibers tend to absorb water in concrete, leading to a reduction in strength. Similar to fibers, straw enhances the ductility of concrete and impacts its fresh, hardened, and durability properties. This report explores various treatments of straw fibers and their effects on the mechanical and durability properties of concrete. This research examines the mechanical properties (compressive strength, flexural strength, and split tensile strength) and durability properties (shrinkage, water absorption, and initial surface absorption) of treated straw-reinforced concrete. Various treatment methods for rice straw, including soaking in water, polymer treatment, hot water treatment (HWT), and NaOH treatment, were employed before incorporating them into concrete. An M30 grade concrete mix was produced with seven different sets: a control mix, dry straw concrete mix, wetted straw concrete mix, HWT straw with 10% cement substituted by silica fume, HWT straw with 20% cement substituted by metakaolin, and NaOH-treated straw concrete. All mixes were cast according to IS code specifications. The test results indicated that hot water treatment of straws, combined with replacing 20% of cement with metakaolin, was the most effective method. This combination (HWT with 20% metakaolin) yielded the highest compressive strength at both 7 and 28 days. Additionally, the inclusion of 20% metakaolin and 10% silica fume in the HWT straw mix resulted in the highest flexural strength. The maximum split tensile strength was also achieved with the HWT straw mix with 20% metakaolin. The presence of rice straw fiber significantly improved the durability properties of concrete.

Keywords: Natural fibers, Synthetic fiber substitution, Fiber reinforced composites, Concrete, Mechanical and Durability Properties, Biodegradable Properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Natural fibers are increasingly used in concrete as a substitute for artificial fibers. Historically, various efforts have been made to replace synthetic fibers with natural fibers in fiber-reinforced composites. These fibrous materials enhance the structural integrity of composite materials. Additionally, natural (vegetable) fibers offer biodegradable properties as renewable resources, contributing to the high performance of composite materials. They provide benefits such as durability, low density, good

mechanical properties, low cost, and environmental advantages along with improved technical performance.

Natural (vegetable) fibers are obtained from sources such as stalks, leaves, seeds, and seed pods. These fibers are used in composites across multiple industries, including transportation, construction, and military applications, as well as in building materials. Natural fiber composites are known for being environmentally friendly. However, natural fibers also present certain challenges, including swelling, degradation, poor chemical resistance, high variability in mechanical properties, high water absorption, and weak bonding within cementitious matrices. Therefore, enhancing the surface texture of natural fibers through various treatments and technologies is of significant interest to address these issues.

2. CLASSIFICATION OF NATURAL FIBERS

Fibers are slender, thread-like materials that can either exist as continuous filaments or as discrete, elongated pieces similar to bits of thread. They serve a variety of purposes, such as being components in composite materials and being used in the production of items like paper or felt by matting them into sheets. Fibers can be broadly categorized into two main types: synthetic (or man-made) fibers and natural fibers. Cellulose-based fibers, as depicted in Figure 1, are divided into two primary categories: wood fibers and non-wood fibers. Non-wood fibers are further classified into straw fibers, plant fibers, and grass fibers. Wood fibers are divided into softwood fibers and hardwood fibers.

Figure 1: Categories of natural fiber (Ni, 1995)

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The primary objectives of this study are:

- To assess the physical characteristics of rice straw fibers following various treatments.
- To predict the mechanical properties of concrete reinforced with treated straw.
- To evaluate the effect of chemical treatments on the durability of straw-reinforced concrete.
- To investigate how chemical treatments of rice straw influence the adhesion properties between the straw and concrete.

4. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

Rice straw, a major by-product of agriculture in India, saw a production of 113 million tonnes in 2018-2019, slightly up from 112.9 million tonnes the previous year. Farmers typically dispose of this straw and stubble residue by burning it in the fields or dumping it into water bodies. While rice straw can be used for cattle feed or paper production, these methods are not widely adopted due to their high costs. Consequently, most farmers resort to burning the straw in the fields, which significantly contributes to air pollution and associated health issues due to carbohydrate emissions (Allam et al., 2011).

In many parts of the world, low-cost housing initiatives aim to meet the rising demand for affordable housing. Depending on the available natural resources, primary housing components are often constructed using bricks or cement block infills, along with straw-reinforced walls and floors. One often underutilized agricultural by-product is rice straw, a cellular non-wood fibrous material. Instead of burning the straw, incorporating it into concrete can create a sustainable, low-cost building material, thereby reducing environmental pollution (Allam et al., 2011).

This study explores the use of rice straw as reinforcement in concrete structures, aiming to enhance the properties of building materials. Rice straw offers several advantages: it is reasonably priced, lightweight, and has a lower environmental impact compared to other materials. When properly treated, straw can provide strength and ductility similar to steel fibers. However, untreated dry straw tends to absorb water from the concrete, leading to reduced strength. Therefore, it is crucial to identify effective treatment methods to minimize the water absorption capacity of straw.

Straw can function as a thermal insulation material, providing benefits such as reduced energy costs and more comfortable indoor temperatures. Rice straw, due to its high silica content, random availability, and relatively low cost, has a significant potential as an efficient secondary raw material among agricultural wastes.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews research on using treated and untreated straw in concrete. Straw can enhance concrete's ductility and affect its fresh and hardened properties, as well as durability. However, its high water absorption capacity necessitates treatments to improve workability and strength.

Munshi et al. (2013) found that replacing cement with Rice Straw Ash (RSA) in mortar improved its compressive strength and setting times, offering a cost-effective construction alternative.

Bouasker et al. (2014) reported that straw fibers increase concrete's water absorption, negatively impacting mechanical strength, emphasizing the need to consider natural fibers' specific properties.

Xie et al. (2016) observed that pretreated rice straw had minimal impact on cement hydration, unlike pristine straw, highlighting the importance of treatment methods.

Farooqi and Ali (2016) showed that untreated wheat straw reinforced concrete (WSRC) had lower compressive strength but higher toughness and elasticity than plain concrete, suggesting benefits for pavement applications.

Chen et al. (2017) highlighted the environmental benefits and thermal insulation of straw in concrete but noted a decrease in compressive strength with higher fiber content.

Guo et al. (2017) found that alkali-treated bamboo fiber improved the toughness and tensile strength of oil well cementitious concrete.

Cai et al. (2017) determined that higher straw fiber content decreased mechanical strength and increased water absorption, with short fibers being more effective.

Ataie (2018) noted that introducing rice straw fibers reduced concrete's compressive and flexural

strengths but increased drying shrinkage. Unwashed fibers significantly increased compressive strength.

Wang and Han (2018) recommended 5%-7% straw fiber content for optimal concrete properties, improving workability, toughness, and insulation.

Mahzabin et al. (2018) found that alkali-treated kenaf fibers enhanced the durability of lightweight foamed concrete by reducing water absorption and shrinkage.

Mohamed et al. (2022) indicated that incorporating recycled coarse aggregate and elastoplastic fiber improved the compressive and tensile strength of high-performance concrete.

Kumar et al. (2023) found that adding fibers to bituminous concrete increased stability and reduced deformation, with sisal fiber showing potential for flexible pavements.

Maafi et al. (2023) demonstrated that polypropylene fibers enhanced the mechanical performance and durability of roller-compacted concrete, with 1 kg/m³ being the optimal fiber content.

Kumar et al. (2023) showed that manufactured sand concrete had lower water absorption and better resistance to chemical attacks and abrasion than conventional sand concrete.

Althoey et al. (2023) found that replacing part of OPC with waste sugarcane ash and silica fume, combined with polypropylene fibers, significantly enhanced ultra-high-performance concrete's mechanical properties.

6. METHODOLOGY ADOPTED IN THE PRESENT STUDY

Based on the objectives of the thesis, the methodology for effectively conducting the research is outlined as follows:

Stage 1: Identifying different treatment methods for natural fibers from literature. Predicting various types of natural fibers used in concrete based on literature review.

Stage 2: Procuring materials and cutting straws to the required size. Conducting preliminary tests, including physical testing of straw, and assessing the physical properties of coarse aggregate, fine aggregate, and cement. Determining the water absorption coefficient of both treated and untreated straws. Applying various treatment methods such as polymer treatment, soaking in normal water, hot water treatment, and NaOH treatment.

Stage 3: Casting specimens of different concrete mix designs and curing them for the required number of days.

Stage 4: Setting up mechanical and durability testing based on standard guidelines. Conducting various tests on straw-reinforced concrete, including compression, flexural, split tensile, water absorption, ISAT, and shrinkage tests, after 7 and 28 days.

Stage 5: Analyzing the mechanical and durability properties of concrete with the addition of treated and untreated rice straw fiber.

Stage 6: Identifying research findings and compiling the research paper and report.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the material characterization of straw-reinforced concrete and investigates the effect of different straw treatments on its absorption capacity. Additionally, the impact of these treatments on the hardened and durability properties of the concrete is examined. The key conclusions drawn from the study are as follows:

- Adding straw fibers to concrete absorbs moisture, reducing workability.

- Hemicellulose in rice straw fibers (RSF) significantly contributes to water absorption due to its higher moisture penetrability compared to cellulose. The presence of hemicellulose affects the interfacial bond between RSF and concrete, while the surface morphology of dry RSF, which includes various pores, increases water intake.
- Removing organic components such as lignin and hemicellulose through hot water treatment (HWT) helps mitigate the hydrophilic nature of the fibers. Treated fibers block water rather than absorb it, resulting in low water absorption and a smooth surface that improves bonding between the fiber and concrete.
- Dry straws absorb water from concrete, creating voids and leading to lower compressive, flexural, and split tensile strengths. The density of voids is higher in dry straw-reinforced concrete.
- Straw pull-out is a common failure mode in straw-reinforced concrete due to the low bond strength.
- Polymer treatment of straws improves compressive, flexural, and tensile strengths but reduces the concrete's workability.
- Concrete with hot water-treated fibers and binding materials (metakaolin and silica fume) exhibits higher flexural and split tensile strengths than other treated fiber-reinforced concretes, due to strong interfacial adhesion between fiber and cementitious matrix.
- Polymer-treated straws have the lowest water absorption coefficient, but during mixing, the polymer layer can separate, resulting in lower strength compared to other treated straws.
- NaOH treatment roughens the straw surface, enhancing bond strength but reducing workability.
- Concrete with hot water-treated straws and 20% metakaolin exhibits higher compressive, flexural, and split tensile strengths compared to other treated straw-reinforced concretes.
- Untreated RSF has a hydrophilic nature and rough surface, leading to higher water absorption. Dry RSF concrete shows maximum water absorption (0.76 ml/m²), while hot water-metakaolin mixed concrete shows minimum flow rate (0.025 ml/m²·s).
- The maximum shrinkage was observed in dry RSF concrete after 30 days. Untreated RSF absorbs water and swells initially, then shrinks during drying. The highest shrinkage of 17.95 m³ was recorded in dry straw concrete over 30 days due to the hydrophilic nature of untreated RSF.

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